

Predict and Analysis of Student Academic Performance Using Data Mining Model

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Abstract— In this research study predicting student's academic performance in advance is of great importance for parents, student's further higher educational institutions and the student itself. Selection of a right academic program and institution at right time can save time, efforts and resources of both parents and educational institutions. To achieve this goal, an intelligent decision support system is essential to predict student's performance prior to their admissions in any academic program and courses or getting promoted to the higher classes in an academic program. Scope of this work is to first identify key features, influencing students' performance, and then develop an accurate predication model for prediction of their performance, prior to taking admission in an intended program or deciding to continue for higher classes and semesters in the same program or to quit the program at this stage. In this research, first, a subjective method is used for identification of academic and socioeconomic features. to develop the prediction model and then a decision tree-based algorithm, Logistic Model Trees, is adopted to learn the intrinsic relationship between the identified features and students' academic grades. The proposed model is trained and tested on a real-world dataset of 1,000+ records, collected from examination database of the M.P. Universities. Simulation of the results is performed in Weka 3.8.6 environment. with its default parameters and 10+ folds cross validation settings. The proposed system achieved predictive accuracy of 85.13%, which guides parents, management of higher educational institutions and students itself to decide whether they should go forward or quit this program or institution at this stage.

Keywords—*data mining, prediction, classification, student's marks/grades prediction, recommendation, decision support system*

I. INTRODUCTION

Appropriate carrier selection is one the key decisions in students' life. A wrongly chosen carrier sometimes destroy students' life. Right carrier selection for a student is always based on selection of right educational program. Usually, students of higher education institutions, management of these institutions and parents follow general trends to select or recommend an educational program at Bachelor and Master Level of studies. This kind of choice is based on educated guess of the stakeholders and usually does not take into account the students personal, academic and socio-economic characteristics. Selection of appropriate educational program needs a prediction system to foresee students' academic performance prior to taking admission or continuing

to classes. However, the development of this intelligent predication system is a challenging tasks due to its dependency on various factors, such as personal, socio- economic, psychological and other factors.

Data mining and Machine learning are the key tools which can better perform in this area and can help to predict students' performance prior to taking admission at Master level programs.

In the proposed study, first, most influencing predictor variables are identified and then a decision tree-based, Logistic Model Trees (LMT) algorithm is adopted to learn the prediction system from students' data, collected from the examination database of University of Peshawar. The data used is of bachelor and master level students. Here, it is important to note that in Asian Countries, specifically Pakistan, the bachelor degree consists of two year's studies, which is followed by two year's master study (16 Grade). In this study, data of bachelor level (14 Grade) students is considered because it is one of the important factors, which decide the students' performance at university level master degree programs.

Key contributions of the paper include:

- Critical analysis of the factors influencing students' academic performance and identification of most important socio-economic, academic and personal predictive features, which play important role in automatically selecting a right Master Degree Program after graduation (bachelor degree).
- Pre-processing of student's academics data and preparation of a cleaned dataset for students' academic performance analysis.
- Design of flexible framework for mining and extraction of hidden intrinsic relationship among students' characteristics and their academic performance.
- Real-time intelligent and accurate decision making and recommendation generation to students intending to take new admission in a master program or planning to continue study in further classes or semesters of an already chosen program.

The rest of paper is organized as follows: Section 2 summarises related work. Section 3 describes methodology. Section 4 describes the data set used in this

research and the associated experiments and results generated using the proposed methods. Section 5 concludes the work done along-with future directions of the proposed research.

II. RELATED WORK

Prediction of students' academic performance is a hot area of research since long. The research community has widely focused on identification of most predictive features influencing students' academic performance at different levels of their studies. V.rameshetal. [1] have identified factors influencing performance of students in final examinations and have worked on finding suitable data mining algorithm(s)for predicting grade of students and giving timely warning to students at risk. They revile that parents' occupation plays a major role in predicting grades. Magdalene et al. [2] conclude that Association Rules Mining is a useful algorithm in this area. They used apriori algorithm to extract a set of rules, specific to each class and analysed the given data to classify the student based on their performance. Manolis Chalaris et al. [3] present capabilitiesof data mining in the context of a Higher Education Institute and try to discover new explicit knowledge by applying data mining techniques to educational data. Pauziah Mohd et al. [4] determined that students' results for the fundamental subjects in the first semester are used as independent variables orinput predictor variables while CGPA at 8thsemester was used as output or dependent variable. They concluded that there is a direct correlation between students' strong academic ability on fundamental subjects at early semester and their overall academic performance upon graduation. They also concluded that Neural Network model is acceptable and can be used to predict student academic performance. Tanveer et al. [5] have predicted students' performance using attributes such as Cumulative Grade Point Average, Quiz, Laboratory, Midterm and Attendance marks. Ibrahim et al., [6] have predicted students' academic performance by their cumulative grade point average (CGPA) upon graduation. In their study, they used students' demographic profile and the CGPA for the first semester of the undergraduate studies as predictor variables for the students' academic performance in the under-graduate degree program. They developed three predictive models, artificial neural network, decision tree and linear regressionusing SAS Enterprise Miner. They claim that all the three models produce an accuracy of more than 80%. They also claim that artificial neural network outperforms the other two models.Quadri et al., [7] have worked to predict dropout ratio of students' using data mining approach. They used decision trees to withdraw important design decisions and explain the interdependencies among the properties of dropout students. Sajadin et al., [8] have applied kernel-based method as data mining techniques to analyse the relationships between students' behavioural data and their successinformation and developed a model of student performance prediction. They used SVM and claim 61 to 93 % accuracy in different cases. Abu Tair et al.[9] have conducted a case study trying to extract useful knowledge from graduate student's data, which is collected from the college of Science and Technology – Khan Younis. The dataset used consistsof fifteen years span from [1993- 2007]. They claimed 71.25% accuracy. Osmanbegović et al.,

[10] have applied three supervised data mining algorithms on the preoperative assessment data for predicting success in a course (either passed or failed) and the performance of the learning methods were evaluated based on predictive accuracy. They proved that Naïve Bayes classifier outperforms neural network methods, and claimed accuracy up to 75%. Ruby et al., [11] have conducted a case study attempting to look into the higher educational domain of data mining to analyse students' performance. They analysed students' data using ID3, J48, NBTree, REPTree, SimpleCart and claimed an accuracy ranging from68-71%. Nguyen et al., [12] have compared accuracy of Decision Tree and Bayesian Network algorithms for predicting academic performance of undergraduate and postgraduate students at different academic institutes andclaimed 86% accuracy. They proved that Decision Tree is consistently 3-12% more accurate than the Bayesian Network. Elakia et al., [13] have conducted a study on data mining in educational database for predicting behavioural patterns of the students. They suggested that various classifiers like ID3 (Iterative Dichotomizer) and C4.5 algorithms can be used to give career suggestion and to find the violent behaviour in a student. Although their study was restrictedto three major groups (bio, comp science, commerce) in higher secondary school, stillthey claimed that ID3 outperforms the other two algorithms in prediction.

State-of-the-art research in the area, discussed above and in [14], consider students' academic characteristics for predicting their academic performance, however socio-economic and demographic characteristics are overlooked, which are focused in this study.

III. PROPOSEDMETHODOLOGY

To accurately recommend students with an appropriate choice for their study at Master level, an intelligent predictive model is proposed. To implement the proposed IDSS for the objective in-hand, a flexible framework of the IDSS is designed, which is shown in Fig.1.

A. Framework of the Proposed Intelligent Decision Support System

The proposed framework, shown in Fig.1, consists of two main components termed as offline stage and online stage.

- **Offline Stage:** In the offline phase, student demographic, personal and academic data is extracted from the Examination Database. The collected is pre-processed and stored.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed intelligent decision support system forstudents' academic performance prediction

(Training Dataset)” in a local file. The key pre-processing steps are explained in the subsequent section. The training dataset is used for creation of “Student Performance Prediction Model”, using Logistic Model Trees (LMT) algorithm.

- **Online Stage:** In this stage, the “Student Performance Prediction Model”, is used to predict performance of the “New Student Data (unseen data)” in the intended Master Program.

B. Feature Extraction

Here, extensive literature study has been performed and detailed subjective discussion is made with experts of education to identify these key influencing features. Authors have identified and categorized the required features into three categories: Demographics, Academic and Socio-economic.

C. Data Pre-processing

For preparation of the dataset, data from University of Peshawar’s examinations database is used for the years 2014-17. The data selected consists of all disciplines. The overall dataset consists of sixteen features with the following distribution among the three categories of features.

- Demographics-category:* gender etc.
- Academic-category:* discipline, mode of study (Regular/Private), current discipline division (CD_Div), previous discipline division (PD Div), previous discipline attempts (PD Attempts), previous discipline unfair means case (PD UFM), current discipline unfair means case (CD UFM), previous discipline courses (PD Combination).
- Socio-economic-category:* institute (CD_Institute), current discipline district (CD District), previous discipline institute (PD Institute), previous discipline district (PD District), LiteracyRate, Human Development Index (HDI) and Poverty of the area. Here, authors have introduced three derived attributes, LiteracyRate, HDI and Poverty of the area the student belongs to. Literacy Rate is derived from the study of [15]. HDI is derived from the [16] and poverty attribute is derived from the [17]. The finally prepared data is stored in “TrainingDataset”, which is further used for Model Creation.

The output or prediction variable used in this study is current discipline Grade (CD Grade).

D. Model Creation

For Creation of the predictive model, Logistic Model Trees (LMT) is used. The proposed LMT induction algorithm is created using 10-folds cross validation with default parameters in Weka 3.8 environment. The model creation process is shown in Algorithm 1.

Proposed Algorithm 1. Creation of Logistic Model Trees (LMT) Prediction Model.

Begin

inputs: d – the given students dataset

LMT – the given learning algorithm

$\bar{Q} = \{e_1 = precision, e_2 = recall, e_3 = accuracy\}$ – the set of evaluation metrics;

output: $p - 1 * m$; matrix of LMT performance on d for \bar{Q} where $m = 3$

F = number of folds;

1 F = 10; P = 0;

2 generate F FOLD; // 10-folds of d

3 for f = 1 to F perform

a. TestData = FOLD [f]; //create test dataset

b. TrainData = $d - \text{TestData}$; //create train dataset

c. Model = creatModel(TrainData, LMT); // create LMT prediction model

d. P = P + addPer(testModel(TestData, Model, \bar{Q});

end for

4 $p = \frac{P}{F}$;

5 return (p)

End

In algorithm 1, *creatModel()* function uses LMT learner and learns *TrainData* for the FOLD [f = 1 to]

E. Model Execution

In this phase students’ grades prediction is performed.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

Weka 3.8 data mining library is used with its default parameters as the simulation tool on a standalone Intel® Core™ i5-4300M CPU @ 2.60GHz system.

B. Evaluation Criteria

F-score, precision, recall, ROC area and classification accuracy are used as evaluation metrics.

C. Dataset

A real world dataset of 1,021 records obtained from University of Peshawar, consisting eight academic features, seven socio-economic features, and one demographic feature is used. Three predictive classes, including 1st Division, 2nd Division and Fail are used.

D. Experiments and Results

Five types of experiments: Experiment-I using academic features (accuracy 79.1%), Experiment-II using socio-economic features (52.4% accuracy), and Experiment-III to V with combinations of Academic and Demographic features, Socio-economic and Demographic features, and Academic, Socio-economic and Demographic features (81.5%, 60.4% and 83.2%, respectively) are used.

Fig. 2. Comparison of predictive accuracies of the proposed methodology using different combinations of the predictive features' categories.

Fig. 2 shows that highest accuracy is obtained when all the three categories of features are combined for creation of testing of the predictive model.

E. Comparison

The proposed model is compared with Random Forest and J48. The results are shown in Table I, in which random forest results are comparable to the proposed methodology.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED LMT ALGORITHM WITH RANDOM FOREST AND J48

Algorithm	Precision	Recall	F-Measure
Proposed Algorithm (Weighted Avg.)	0.838	0.835	0.835
Random Forest Weighted Avg.	0.833	0.831	0.831
J48 Weighted Avg.	0.794	0.791	0.790

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The proposed model has achieved predictive accuracy of 83.09%. Future work will focus on missing predictors.

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